

Commentary Revisions

Request From	Comment to Address	Notes
Peer-reviewer	Implementation of the authors recommendations will take a huge effort and likely be an uphill battle, but these should all be read, understood, and considered. The authors take note of many of the ongoing strategies for dealing with OPSW, but I am not sure there was a focus on the creation of demonstration pit lakes, which themselves have raised significant controversy.	We thank the reviewer for this comment and completely agree that the demonstration pit lakes are controversial and full of challenges. The only full-scale commercial demonstration pit lake that we are aware of is Syncrude's Base Mine Lake. We have added text (page 11, lines 6-7) as well as a reference to Syncrude's 2021 report showing that chronic toxicity persists.
Peer-reviewer	It is great that the authors suggested solutions to the existing problems, but it would be more convincing if the authors provided examples of successful applications of the suggested solutions.	We appreciate your recognition of the solutions proposed. The European Industry Emissions Portal is a good start as an example of a public website for data exchange that we could use as a model. We've added reference to this on page 20, lines 7-9. If there are any other examples that the peer-reviewer is aware of that we should consider adding, please let us know.
Peer-reviewer	Please provide references to the studies that found a direct connection between oil sands tailings with human health	We have added text to address this on Page 8, line 17 to page 9 line 15. To have a direct connection, studies would need to be done. We are not aware of any. We contacted the Fort Chip Nation and they are not aware of anything either.

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Peer-reviewer	In places, the authors come across as implying that the government knows more than the public and tries to hide the evidence. Please provide evidence/references for this view. As examples, see the abstract (lines 12-13) and Page 19, lines 6-7: "Information asymmetry exists: oil; oilsands mine operators and governments know more about the risks than those that will be asked to accept them." Please avoid general statements without providing evidence.	Text added on page 6-13 regarding internal data on naphthenic acids and the Alberta Energy Regulator and Imperial Oil's concealment of an industrial wastewater spill for 9 months.
Peer-reviewer	Provide full name of abbreviations (OSPW, TRVs in the Multicriteria Decision Framework, page 31).	Done
Peer-reviewer	Line 4-8, Page 9. Please merge the references. There are two sets of similar references.	We are not seeing it. The references in that section appear to be unique.
Handling Editor	This is only a minor issue, but the authors should update their supplementary materials to give the files plain English names, so the user does not have to open them to identify what they are about.	Done
Handling Editor	The figures in the manuscript require numbers and legends.	Done

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Handling Editor	The opposition of indigenous communities to the treat-and-release proposal seems key to establishing the argument and may be fundamental to illustrating the principle of “polluter pays”, yet is first mentioned on page 12 almost as an aside. Bringing this forward to the introduction may strengthen the framing of the whole article.	Agree. The position of the Indigenous groups has been moved up to page 10, line 17-21. We think this is a good place for it, after giving some background and discussing the composition and toxicity of the ponds.
Handling Editor	I wonder if what the authors mean by “no further exposure” could be further developed and clarified. Is this about using current exposure levels as a regulatory baseline, and ensuring that treatment and other options for the tailing ponds do not increase exposure levels relative to this baseline? The authors talk about measurement of exposure and violation of the principle, so I think I can piece together what they mean, but as a core part of the paper I think it would be worth reviewing the section and the authors making sure they are satisfied their meaning is absolutely explicit.	We agree and understood from this that the central message was not clear. To make it clear, we reimagined Figure 2 and created two parts (Figure 2A and 2B) with detailed figure legends to describe “No further exposure” as it stands within the framework of the multicriteria framework. We also rearranged the text for clarity and provided an example that illustrates “No further exposure” on page 15 line 22 to page 16, line 12. We also created audio recordings explaining Figure 2A-B. If there is a mechanism available to upload these, please let us know.
Handling Editor	In relation to the above, I am not quite sure I follow the role of indicator species in “no further exposure”. Is it that changes in the populations of these species should be used as an indicator in change of exposure profile from the current baseline? I am similarly not quite clear about the use of monitoring data of other kinds, and the role of trend analysis in the authors proposals. The solution might just be a matter of deliberate breaking down of the idea to its constituent parts, introducing each of these, and showing how they can be assembled into a regulatory solution for pollution from OSPW.	Re: Indicator species. No. Change in indicator species populations can not be used as an indicator in exposure because these changes could be due to other factors. However, change in indicator species parameters (numbers, health etc) should be used to trigger assessment of what caused the change. Figure 2 now explains this better we hope. If Figure 2 should also explain the other issues mentioned.
Handling Editor	The final recommendations are clear. I have just a minor thought that recommendation 5 and 3 might be of the same piece, so could be addressed together, but I could be wrong.	They are related but separate. For example, 5 includes risk analysis/modelling of cost-effectiveness for things like the cost of cleanup versus the reduction in human health and environmental risks to current and future generations

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Handling Editor	<p>There are some issues with transition between and introduction of arguments, where it can feel like the authors are perhaps overstating some claims (e.g. page 7 line 19-20; page 8 line 21). This may be a consequence of a tendency, in some places, to make a strong claim before making the argument for the claim. This gives some claims a rather sudden and heavy landing, when in fact the claim seems well-justified by the subsequent argument.</p>	<p>We have taken a less dramatic stance in that section (page 7, line 19-20. With respect to page 8 line 21, we read this paragraph over, and thought this was more a stylistic preference. We liked the way the text read the way it is.</p>
Handling Editor	<p>In relation to presentation of argument, the subsection on TRVs shows some opportunity for improvement. This is an example of where the rhetorical flow of the argument puts the cart before the horse, with the point being argued toward being placed after the argument rather than before it. Similarly, the concluding paragraph of the “no further exposure” section on p13 is an example where the authors tie all the preceding concepts together in a summary, but only after they have been through the argument rather than before. If the summary is presented first, the reader can follow the argument to a known destination, rather than having to try to piece together the destination from the argument while trying to understand the argument.</p>	<p>We agree and believe we have improved the TRV section. We have rearranged the text for clarity</p>
No One	<p>Added a section on risk tolerance</p>	<p>We felt this was an important addition. Please review.</p>